

Stellar Bobbing Motion in the Early Milky Way Galaxy

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Received : 30 12 2024; accepted : 30 12 2024

Abstract. This study explores how the gravitational influences of dark matter led to the evolution of stellar scaleheight in the early Milky Way galaxy. During the formation period of the Milky Way galaxy, a minimal metallicity environment facilitated the formation of metal-poor stars primarily within a 3.43 kpc radius, with distributions extending to 5 kpc. Deficient in rotational support, the chaotic inner galaxy experienced disc heating, leading to an increase in the tangential scaleheight of these stars, thickening the inner disc. Non-baryonic dark matter, concentrated perpendicularly to the disc within an 8 kpc radius, gravitationally influenced these stars, accelerated their motion in the opposite trajectory of the upward tangential motion and decreased their scaleheight. As these stars approached the disc of the Milky Way galaxy, gravitational drag situated these stars into a stable, thin disc structure. The study concludes that this dynamic process, driven by dark matter, decreases single “bobbing motion” in stellar scaleheights, transitioning over time into stable disc motion, shaping the Milky Way’s early disc evolution.

Keywords. stars: kinematics and dynamics–Galaxy: stellar content–cosmology: dark matter.

1. Introduction

Dark matter has a gravitational influence, which is an indispensable component that substantially contributes to the evolution of the Milky Way galactic disc. According to my observations, a prior study has demonstrated the contribution of dark matter to the thickening of the galactic disc (Church *et al.* 2019). But this investigation specifically evades the earlier period of the galaxy and provides insight into the increasing thickness of the galaxy’s inner and outer regions in recent times. On the other hand, another prior study suggests that the thick disc in the galaxy formed only in the inner region during the early period, and over time the inner disc steadily transformed into a thin disc (Ciucă *et al.* 2021). However, this study did not provide any explanation regarding the contribution of dark matter. Based on observations from existing literature, I observe that the motion of stars within specific regions of the inner disc exhibited a single bobbing motion in earlier periods, which was influenced by dark matter. I will present my findings in this paper through a simple astrophysical model and observations from existing literature. In this presentation, I will explain after star formation in the galaxy’s inner region during the earlier period how the scaleheight of stars increased and the gravitational influence of dark matter contributed to the decrease in scaleheight, leading to the formation of a thin and sta-

ble disc.

2. Discussion

The presence of a substantially minimal rate of metallicity in the early Milky Way galaxy induced the formation of metal-poor stars within the first few billion years after galaxy formation (Howes *et al.* 2015; Ardern-Arentsen *et al.* 2024). Although the majority of these metal-poor stars formed within the inner region of the galaxy, within a 3.43 kpc radius (Howes *et al.* 2015), their distribution extended up to a radius of approximately 5 kpc (Ardern-Arentsen *et al.* 2024). At that time, rotational support for stars was not properly initiated (Belokurov & Kravtsov 2022), and the chaotic environment of the galaxy led to disc heating (Chandra *et al.* 2024), which induced the tangential scaleheight of metal-poor stars to begin increasing. By increasing their scale height, metal-poor stars played a role in thickening the inner region of the galaxy’s disc throughout the earlier period. In galaxies of similar mass to the Milky Way, the non-baryonic nature of dark matter was present in the inner region during an earlier period (Graaff *et al.* 2024). On the other hand, by observing the presence of the same non-baryonic nature of dark matter in the inner region of the Milky Way galaxy (Grand & White 2022), I have concluded that this dark

matter was present in the Milky Way during an earlier period. The excess amount of dark matter in the inner region of the Milky Way galaxy was distributed perpendicular to the galactic disc (Grand & White 2022). The stars that had already attained a specific scaleheight and contributed to the formation of the thick disc had their motion deflected by the gravitational potential of this dark matter, which accelerated their motion in the opposite trajectory of the upward tangential motion toward the plane of the Milky Way galactic disc. As a result stars at a high scaleheight steadily decrease in their scaleheight, and when these stars approach the galactic disc through the decrease in scaleheight, the gravitational drag of the galactic disc situates the stars into the disc, playing a role in the formation of a stable and thin disc.

I am presenting a simple astrophysical model to explain how a star at a high scaleheight descends onto the disc.

Here, I assume that the spatial nature of dark matter is spherically symmetric and flat (Grand & White 2022).

$$\Phi_{DM}(z) = \frac{4}{3}\pi G\rho_{DM}z^2 \quad (1)$$

In this model z is the height of the star from the disc of the Milky Way galaxy, G is the gravitational constant, Φ_{DM} defines the gravitational influence induced by the potential of dark matter that accelerates the motion of the stars towards the disc, and ρ_{DM} is the density of dark matter. While in earlier periods there was plenty of dark matter in the galactic disc, so the density of dark matter was substantially higher. I observed that as the density of dark matter increases then its gravitational influence asserts greater intensity (Saxton *et al.* 2016), which plays a role in the decrease in the height of the stars.

$$F_{DM}(z) = -\frac{d\Phi_{DM}}{dz} = -\frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho_{DM}z \quad (2)$$

I assume that F_{DM} defines the gravitational force induced by the potential of dark matter.

Since stars contributed to the formation of a thin disc through the decrease in scaleheight, I consider the Milky Way galaxy disc to be a thin disc.

$$\Phi_{disc}(z) = 2\pi G \Sigma z^2 \quad (3)$$

In this model Σ is the density of the plane of the Milky Way galaxy and Φ_{disc} is the gravitational potential of the plane of the Milky Way galaxy which contributes to the situating of stars within the disc.

$$F_{disc}(z) = -\frac{d\Phi_{disc}}{dz} = -4\pi G \Sigma z \quad (4)$$

Again, I assume that F_{disc} defines the gravitational force of the the plane of Milky Way galaxy.

$$\frac{d^2z(t)}{dt} = -\frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho_{DM}z - 4\pi G \Sigma z \quad (5)$$

3. Conclusion

In this study, I observed that in earlier galaxies, dark matter was distributed perpendicularly to the disc within the inner region, specifically within an 8 kpc radius (Grand & White 2022). Speculating from this concept, I have concluded that in earlier times, the motion of stars in the inner region of the galaxy, following star formation, caused a single bobbing motion through the increase and decrease of scaleheight. This bobbing motion was present within the 5-10 kpc radius of the galactic disc during that period. The distribution of dark matter with the evolution of the galaxy, leads the stars' bobbing motion to steadily transition into normal motion on the disc.

Acknowledgements

I acknowledge all authors whose works were referenced in this manuscript, as well as OpenAI's ChatGPT(chat.openai.com) for their assistance in writing it.

DataAvailability

This work is comprehensively theoretical and does not rely on any observational or experimental data. The finding presented in this paper is original, and the contributions of the authors referenced are taken entirely from publicly available sources, which are cited in the reference section of the manuscript. The equations used in the mathematical analysis are based on fundamental principles of astrophysics, interpreted and explained from the perspective of this study.

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